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Patent Applications in Italian Regions

The patent applications in Italian regions decreased by -1.91% between 2018 and 2023.

The European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) calculates the number of patent applications in Italian regions. The indicator is a ratio: the numerator is the number of patent applications filed with the European Patent Office, and the denominator is the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Purchasing Power Standards (PPS). The ability of companies to develop new products will determine their competitive advantage. One measure of the innovation rate of new products is the number of patents. The data refers to the 20 Italian regions between 2018 and 2023.

Patent Applications in Italian Regions in 2023. Northern Italian regions, such as Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lombardy, Piedmont, and Veneto, show the highest values, with Emilia Romagna at the top with an impressive 98.94. These figures are not surprising, considering the established reputation of these areas for their strong manufacturing and technological industries, as well as the dynamic business environment that supports innovation and research. Lombardy and Veneto, in particular, benefit from an ecosystem of mature companies and start-ups, in addition to high-quality universities and research centers that foster the continuous generation of new ideas and patentable products. Conversely, regions like Basilicata, Calabria, and Sicily record the lowest values, respectively 33.45, 40.13, and 39.82. This reflects the persistent challenges in southern Italy, where the economic and research infrastructure may be less developed and where companies might have less access to funding and support for research and development activities. These regions could benefit from targeted policies to stimulate innovation and entrepreneurship, as well as investments in education and research that could translate into an increase in innovation capacity. Interesting is also the analysis of regions like Tuscany and Marche, which show relatively high values of 79.42 and 70.24. This may indicate a fertile environment for innovation in specific sectors, such as the biomedical sector for Tuscany, which boasts a robust health and biotechnology sector. Additionally, Liguria and Umbria, with values of 66.86 and 63.75, show that even smaller regions can effectively compete in the innovative landscape thanks to niches of specialization and effective regional policies in supporting research and development. These data clearly indicate that innovation capacity, measured through patent applications, is a critical factor for the competitive advantage of regions. Companies that can develop new products through technological innovation not only contribute to the economic progress of their region but also strengthen Italy's position in the global market. The challenge for Italy remains to reduce the gap between the north and south in the field of innovation, ensuring that even less advanced regions can participate more actively in the innovation economy.

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Patent Applications in Italian Regions between 2018 and 2023. Molise, with a percentage increase of 24.47%, shows the most remarkable growth in terms of patent applications, rising from 38.34 in 2018 to 47.72 in 2023. This could indicate a renewed focus on R&D activities and an effective regional strategy for supporting innovation. Similarly, Campania and Abruzzo have recorded significant percentage increases (16.11% and 14.49%, respectively), suggesting a favorable environment for innovation and potentially greater investment in key technological sectors. In contrast, regions like Friuli Venezia Giulia and Tuscany have seen a marked reduction in the number of patents, with declines of 26.08% and 8.90%. These contractions could reflect various factors, such as changes in economic priorities, reduced investments in specific sectors, or the natural volatility in the pace of producing patentable innovations. Particularly, the drastic decrease in Friuli Venezia Giulia might indicate a significant crisis or restructuring in the local industrial fabric. Liguria, Lazio, and Lombardy also show a decrease, albeit more contained, possibly highlighting a saturation or a shift in the focused areas of research and development. Valle d'Aosta and Umbria also register a slight decline, potentially indicative of broader economic difficulties or an ongoing transition in key sectors. On the other hand, regions like Veneto and Piedmont show positive, albeit moderate, growth with increases of 3.25% and 1.48%, respectively. This is consistent with their role as well-established industrial hubs and research centers capable of maintaining a steady flow of innovations. The case of Emilia Romagna is particularly interesting: despite a slight percentage decrease, it maintains a very high volume of patent applications. This suggests that, despite a small contraction, the region remains a vital hub of R&D activities in Italy. These regional trends show how innovation can be influenced by a complexity of factors, including economic changes, innovation support policies, access to funding for research and development, and global market dynamics.

Macro-Regions in Italy between 2018 and 2023. From 2018 to 2023, the South shows a positive increase both in absolute terms (+2.91) and percentage (+7.13%). This increase can be interpreted as a sign of revitalization of innovative activity in these regions, traditionally less involved in innovation processes compared to the North. This growth is the result of R&D incentive policies, investments in tech start-ups, and greater involvement of universities and research centers in the technology transfer process. On the contrary, the North and Central regions show an opposite trend, with a decrease both in absolute terms (North: -3.84, Center: -4.22) and percentage terms (North: -4.63%, Center: -5.93%). This decline could reflect several factors, such as market saturation, the relocation of R&D activities to other more cost-competitive areas, or the natural fluctuation of innovation in sectors that have already reached technological development peaks in the past. The contrast between growth in the South and decline in the North and Center raises important questions regarding balance and territorial cohesion in terms of innovation capacity. While the South seems to be on a recovery path, the North and Center may need to renew their strategies to maintain competitiveness. This could include strengthening synergies between industry and academic research, reviving incentives for high-tech companies, and providing greater support for the commercialization of innovations. Additionally, the significant negative variation in the North and Center might indicate the need for a deeper reflection on innovation support policies and resource distribution, ensuring that incentives and opportunities are not concentrated only in certain areas but distributed more equitably to stimulate a more resilient and diversified economic and industrial fabric throughout the country.

North-South Divide. The South has shown a positive increase from 2018 to 2023, with a 7.13% rise in the number of patent applications, suggesting an improvement in innovative activity. However, the

total number of patent applications in the South remains significantly lower than in the North, even though the North has seen a reduction of 4.63% in the same period. Similarly, the Center has recorded a decrease of 5.93%, indicating that these regions are also facing challenges. This scenario reflects a persistent gap between the North, historically more industrialized with a stronger economic fabric, and the South, which has historically struggled with less industrialization and R&D investments. Despite recent improvements in the South, the overall gap between these areas remains evident, with the North continuing to dominate in terms of total innovation volume measured through patent applications. The divide underscores the importance of targeted regional development strategies that can balance innovation opportunities across the country, further stimulating innovative activity in the South while supporting the Central and Northern regions to maintain and strengthen their competitiveness.

Economic Policies. To rejuvenate innovation in Italian regions, various economic policies can be adopted to incentivize research and development. An effective strategy begins with the introduction of tax incentives, such as tax credits and deductions, for companies investing in R&D. This would alleviate the financial burden of innovation and stimulate investments in new technologies. Extending these benefits to collaborations between companies and academic institutions could further enhance shared innovation. Increasing funding for research infrastructure in universities, especially in less developed regions, would create the necessary foundations to support their innovative activities. Establishing science and technology parks would act as catalysts for the growth of start-ups and university spin-offs, creating a fertile environment for innovation. For start-ups and SMEs, incubation and acceleration programs offering access to mentoring, investor networks, and logistical support are essential to guide the early stages of entrepreneurial development. These programs should be accompanied by credit guarantees and financial facilitations that would alleviate the economic risk of innovation. Investing in education and training specific to the skills required in R&D would be crucial. Encouraging the integration of entrepreneurship education into academic curricula from primary education to university could prepare a new generation for innovation. Furthermore, promoting international collaborations and networking through events like fairs and conferences would expand learning and business opportunities. From a legislative standpoint, simplifying the bureaucratic processes for patent filing and ensuring effective protection of intellectual property rights are fundamental steps to make innovation more accessible and secure. Finally, using European and national funds to directly finance innovative projects in key sectors such as biotechnology, IT, renewable energy, and nanotechnology could have a significant impact on the economic development of different regions.

Conclusions. The value of patent applications decreased between 2018 and 2023 from an amount of 63.77 units to a value of 62.55 units, a decline of -1.91%. If we look at the Italian macro-regions, we can see that patent applications grew between 2018 and 2023 in Southern Italy by 7.13%, while they decreased in the North by -4.63% and in Central Italy by -4.22%. However, the 2023 data highlights a significant disparity between the Central-Northern regions, which have medium-high levels of patent applications, and Southern Italy, which is significantly behind the more innovative areas of the country.

Declarations

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Appendix

Domande di brevetto nel 2018 e nel 2023

Variazione delle domande di brevetto (2018-2023)

Variazione Percentuale delle Domande di Brevetto per Regione (2018-2023)